

Project CHANGES - Spoke 5

D2.3 – Report on monitoring strategies and preventive conservation guidelines of heritage objects at degradation risk– v1.5

Deliverable information

1

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3

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No.	Name of Partner	Acronym	Role
1	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	CNR (SCITEC, ISPC, IAC)	Spoke leader (ISPC)
2	University of Bologna	UNIBO	Member
2	University of Napoli Federico II	UNINA	Member
4	Sapienza University of Rome...	UNIROMA1	Member
	University of Catania	UNICT	Affiliated by "Convenzione"
5	Opificio delle Pietre Dure	OPD	Spoke co-leader

Executive Summary

In continuity with the outcomes described in Deliverables D2.1 and D2.2, this document details the strategic contribution of the implemented advanced analytical methodologies to the monitoring and assessment of complex degradation pathways in cultural heritage objects.

Through a multi-material approach encompassing paint, textile, stone, metal, and paper-based items, the study bridges the gap between laboratory investigations, in situ analysis and collection management, offering recommendations to optimize the preventive conservation guidelines of these heritage objects.

Table of contents

1. Introduction	p. 6	5
2. Monitoring strategies and preventive conservation guidelines	p. 7	
2.1 Paintings and dyed textiles	p. 7	
2.1.1 <i>Non-invasive monitoring of pigments degradation under variable humidity, temperature and pH conditions using X-ray-based techniques</i>	p. 8	
2.1.2 <i>Multi-scale and multi-technique monitoring and prediction of pigments and dyes degradation driven by light, humidity, and binder composition</i>	p. 12	
2.2 Stones	p. 15	
2.3 Metals	p. 18	
2.4 Works on paper	p. 24	
3. Conclusions	p. 31	
4. References	p. 36	
Annex A. List of research products WP2	p. 40	

1. Introduction

Representing a critical expansion of the research established in deliverables D2.1 and D2.2, this document delineates the latest research findings of the Consortium within the framework of Spoke 5, Work Package 2.

Its focus is the definition of monitoring strategies and the formulation of tailored recommendations to enhance preventive conservation guidelines for heritage objects vulnerable to degradation.

Building upon the comprehensive evidence presented in deliverables D2.1 and D2.2, Section 2 outlines specific proposals for degradation monitoring methodologies and suggests strategic conservation improvements for specific cultural heritage material classes. These include selected families of copper-, sulfide-, lead-, and cobalt-based pigments within oil, polysaccharide, or alkyd binders, alongside triarylmethane dyes on cotton (par. 2.1); natural and artificial stones (par. 2.2); silver-based artifacts (par. 2.3), and paper-based substrates (par. 2.4).

To conclude, Section 3 organizes the final remarks into a series of tables, aimed at facilitating a more efficient and immediate assessment of the research outcomes.

2. Monitoring strategies and preventive conservation guidelines

7

2.1 Paintings and dyed textiles

Research activities on paintings and dyed textiles have focused on the study of the properties and reactivity of specific pigments and dyes. By integrating systematic studies on artificially aged mock-ups with selected case studies, analytical strategies have been developed to identify the factors driving alteration and to characterize neo-formed compounds (for further details cfr. Deliverables D2.1 and D2.2). In parallel, innovative methodologies, sometimes supported by mathematical modelling, have been defined for monitoring and predicting degradation processes.

In addition to highlighting the necessity of controlling exposure to specific lighting conditions and moisture levels, this research proposes innovative non-invasive strategies for monitoring alterations over time. These tools are essential for supporting the implementation of effective preventive conservation guidelines for paintings and dyed textiles in museum collections. To this end, CNR-ISPC (Catania) has established a novel non-invasive analytical protocol based on X-ray techniques to monitor alteration processes within paint. Meanwhile, CNR-SCITEC, in collaboration with CNR-IAC and UNIBO, has optimized monitoring strategies for degradation processes across selected classes of pigments and dyes. This was achieved by means of an integrated, multi-scale and multi-technique approach that, in the case of cadmium yellow pigments, includes mathematical modelling, as described in the sections below.

2.1.1 Non-invasive monitoring of pigments degradation under variable humidity, temperature and pH conditions using X-ray-based techniques (CNR-ISPC, Catania: Andolina R., Arcidiacono T., Caliri C., Falcone F., Ravan E. L., Romano F. P.)

8

This section presents the results obtained from the analytical investigation of both reference and artificially aged mock-ups developed by CNR-ISPC (Catania). The adopted analytical strategy followed a multimodal and correlative approach, integrating complementary mobile X-ray-based techniques, specifically micro-XRF imaging, 1D and 3D CXRF imaging, and MA-XRPD. The combination of these methods enabled the identification of alteration phases formed during the artificial aging experiments carried out to establish new and more suitable guidelines for the preventive conservation of pictorial artworks. The materials examined in this study include orpiment and realgar, silver gilding, smalt, and lead white, all exposed to different environmental stresses such as high relative humidity % (RH %), temperature (T), pH variations, and UV–VIS light (see Deliverables D2.1 and D2.2 for details). The results indicate that these parameters may play a key role in shaping conservation guidelines, as they can induce changes in the visual appearance of painted surfaces.

Orpiment and realgar. UV–VIS light is commonly recognized as a major driver in the transformation of orpiment and realgar into arsenolite or As–S polymorphs [1–3]. However, the experimental data show that additional degradation products can also form in the absence of light. Under slightly alkaline conditions, high RH %, and 40 °C in a closed environment, sulfur crystals developed on the surface of painted mock-ups, irrespective of the binder.

The same alteration phase was identified on the Book of the Dead of Kha at the Egyptian Museum in Turin (cfr. Deliverable D2.2). These findings suggest that **factors other than light exposure may catalyze degradation processes** that ultimately modify the color appearance of the original pictorial layer.

Silver gilding. Silver leaf in paintings typically darkens or tarnishes through the formation of silver sulfides, oxides, or chlorides [4]. To clarify the environmental triggers responsible for this phenomenon, mock-ups were subjected to different conditions. **Darkening occurred in desiccators under slightly alkaline pH, high RH %, 40 °C, and absence of light** in samples prepared with an orpiment-based mordant, consistent with medieval gilding practice [5]. MA-XRPD proved highly effective in identifying secondary crystalline phases contributing to surface darkening. Similar results were observed in various panel paintings by Margarito d'Arezzo; specifically, chlorargyrite was identified in both painted mock-ups and these historical artworks (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. A) Elemental map of residual silver (Ag–L) from the original gilding on *Madonna col Bambino in trono* (or *Madonna di Montelungo*) by Margarito d’Arezzo (1250 ca.; Museo Statale d’Arte Medievale e Moderna, Arezzo, Italy), acquired through MA-XRF scanning with a lateral resolution of 0.5 mm and 18 ms dwell time per pixel; B) Elemental maps of silver (Ag–L) and chlorine (Cl–K) obtained by μ -XRF imaging in the selected region performed with a lateral resolution of 0.1 mm and an acquisition time of 15 ms per pixel; C) Distribution map of chlorargyrite (AgCl) acquired through MA-XRD scanning over an area of 5.5×6.5 cm² with a spatial resolution of 1 mm and an acquisition time of 11 s per pixel; D) XRD spectrum extracted from the mapping, showing diffraction peaks corresponding to metallic silver, chlorargyrite (AgCl), and calcium sulfates (gypsum and anhydrite) forming the preparatory layer.

Smalt. Smalt frequently undergoes deterioration, resulting in color loss and significant alterations in the overall appearance of paintings. Several mechanisms have been proposed to explain this progressive discoloration [6–8]. Experimental results showed that **high RH % in closed environments promote silicate network disruption and potassium leaching**, enhancing the reactivity of Co^{2+} ions and leading to the formation of cobalt-based aggregates.

Micro-XRF and 3D-CXRF imaging effectively monitored the degradation state of smalt paint layers. In stratigraphies simulating historical paintings (smalt over a cerussite-based ground), MA-XRPD detected the formation of lead oxalate after only a few months of accelerated aging, suggesting that such artificial environments foster its development.

Lead white. Lead white blackening is a well-documented alteration process in historical paintings [9]. Experimental evidence indicates that, **beyond the known influence of alkaline pH and pollutants, neutral to acidic pH combined with high RH % can also promote darkening**. In mock-ups composed of an orpiment layer over cerussite, both mixed with egg yolk, MA-XRPD identified two lead dioxide polymorphs, scrutinyite and plattnerite, distributed within the stratigraphy in regions adjacent to the orpiment interface.

Results indicate that controlled environmental conditions, particularly **high RH % and varying pH, significantly influence the chemical behavior of the aged samples**, and that **X-ray-based techniques are well suited for assessing the effects of these treatments**. Systematic investigations of pigment behavior in different chemical environments proved effective in predicting degradation pathways, establishing a basis for the development of preventive conservation guidelines.

2.1.2 Multi-scale and multi-technique monitoring and prediction of pigments and dyes degradation driven by light, humidity, and binder composition (CNR-SCITEC, Perugia/UNIPG: Cartechini L., Costantino C., Doherty B., Mattana S., Monico L., Pinto C., Rosi F., Romani A.; CNR-IAC: Natalini R., Pezzella M.; UNIBO: Gatti L., Prati S., Sciutto G.)

12

The study conducted by CNR-SCITEC (Perugia), in collaboration with CNR-IAC and UNIBO, on artificial paint and dyed-textile mock-ups, utilizing a multi-technique approach across various length scales (see Deliverables D2.1 and D2.2 for details). The findings, presented below, provide essential evidence to support the optimization of preventive conservation guidelines.

Emerald green oil paints (CNR-SCITEC, Perugia, and UNIPG: Cartechini L., Costantino C., Monico L., Rosi F., Romani A.). **UVA-visible light** has been identified as one of the primary drivers behind the transformation of emerald green (a copper arsenite acetate pigment) into **arsenic (V) compounds** on the paint surface. Similar degradation products, exhibiting comparable stratigraphic distributions, were observed in several late 19th and early 20th-century paintings by artists such as James Ensor and Robert Delaunay, confirming that light exposure triggers the long-term alteration of the original pigment. Conversely, **high RH %** promotes alternative reaction pathways for emerald green, resulting in the formation of **arsenolite**.

As K-/Cu K-edges μ -XAS and non-invasive external reflection FT-IR spectroscopy proved to be **effective techniques to monitor the degradation state of emerald green paints**.

These findings were detailed in two 2025 publications in *Science Advances* [10] and *La Rivista del Nuovo Cimento* [11], followed by a dissemination article in *Sapere Scienza* [12].

Arsenic sulfide (orpiment and realgar) paints (CNR-SCITEC, Perugia, and UNIPG: Monico L., Romani A.; UNIBO: Gatti L., Prati S., Sciutto G.). The study conducted by CNR-SCITEC (Perugia) in collaboration with UNIBO on naturally aged paint mock-ups highlights the **critical role of the binder in driving the transformation of arsenic sulfide pigments into arsenic (V) and sulfate species**. Under identical environmental conditions, the degradation process appears to be strictly dependent on the binder used. Comprehensive **As K-/S K-edge XAS and IR analyses of the paint layers** (including the front, reverse of paint fragments, and corresponding cross-sections) revealed that **degradation proceeds rapidly in the presence of linseed oil**. In contrast, **no conversion to arsenic (V) and sulfate** was observed when the same pigments were mixed with **polysaccharide binders (such as arabic gum) or alkyd resins**. This different behavior likely stems from the chemical nature of drying oils. Their film-forming properties result from an autoxidation process that generates a high concentration of reactive intermediates, specifically alkoxy and peroxy radicals. These highly oxidative species are thought to trigger the conversion of arsenic (III) and sulfur (-II) to arsenic (V) and sulfur (VI), respectively.

A collaborative paper detailing these findings is currently in preparation.

Cadmium sulfide (cadmium yellow) oil paints (CNR-SCITEC, Perugia, and UNIPG: Mattana S., Monico L., Rosi F., Romani A.; CNR-IAC: Natalini R., Pezzella M.). A combination of **S K-edge μ -XANES imaging and non-invasive ER-IR spectroscopy**, was employed to monitor **degradation under light and high humidity, revealing the threshold at which the conversion of CdS to cadmium sulfate begins**.

Experimental data from artificially aged paint mock-ups are being used to **refine a mathematical model** developed by CNR-IAC (for details see [13]) to predict the photodegradation of cadmium yellow.

14

The ultimate objective is to provide a predictive tool for the photodegradation of cadmium yellow oil paints, with the potential for future application to other light-sensitive pigments. A paper detailing these results is currently in preparation and is expected to be submitted soon.

Triarylmethane dyes (TAMs) on cotton (CNR-SCITEC, Perugia, and UNIPG: Doherty B., Monico L., Pinto C., Romani A.). This research successfully combines non-invasive in situ and laboratory-based methods to examine the fading of the blue-green background in an 1885 printed cotton dress (Accession Number T.7–1926) from the Victoria and Albert Museum. **Non-invasive UV-VIS-NIR (imaging and single point mode)** combined with **micro-destructive Surface Enhanced Raman spectroscopy** allowed mapping TAM-based dyes distribution and identified their fading pathways.

To better understand these processes, textile mock-ups dyed with Diamond Green G (DGG), Diamond Green B (DGB), and Yellowish Light Green SF (YLG) were prepared and exposed to UVA-VIS light. Controlled photo-induced progressive **N-dealkylation and oxidative degradation via aromatic ring disruption, leading to the formation of photoproducts such as benzophenone derivatives**. A comparison between photo-aged mock-ups and the dress fabric confirmed that DGG was the primary dye involved.

These findings provide critical insights into the **poor lightfastness of TAMs**, informing conservation strategies. To preserve such sensitive artifacts, it is

recommend **minimizing exposure to both natural and artificial light, using either neutral-density filters or precise lighting adjustments.** Full details of this study have been published in [14].

15

2.2 Stones (UNIROMA1: Medeghini L., Di Fazio M.; UNICT: Belfiore C. M., Menta S., Stroschio A.; CNR-IAC: Bretti G., Natalini R., De Filippo B., Pezzella M.)

Research activities have focused on the study of the influence of environmental factors on the durability of both natural (e.g., limestone, white Carrara marble, and travertine) and artificial (mortars) stone materials, aiming at understanding their degradation mechanisms, also in relation to the intrinsic characteristics of the material. To this end, a combination of controlled laboratory tests, was used on properly prepared mock-ups, aimed at determining the hydric behavior of different geomaterials in terms of water absorption by capillarity and full immersion, as well as their resistance to degradation caused by salt crystallization.

The combination of these methods enabled:

- a) understanding the decay behavior of the examined stone materials;**
- b) identifying those parameters which play a key role in the degradation process of each geomaterial;**
- c) establishing suitable guidelines for their preventive conservation.**

The results indicate that water plays a critical role in the degradation of both natural and artificial stone materials. When environmental humidity is high, porous stones readily absorb moisture, which migrates through their pore networks and can carry dissolved salts and pollutants. As the absorbed water evaporates during periods of lower humidity, salts crystallize within the pores,

generating internal stress that led to micro-fracturing, surface scaling, and loss of cohesion [15]. Repeated cycles of wetting and drying intensify these effects, accelerating deterioration over time [16, 17].

16

In artificial stone materials, such as mortars, durability is strongly influenced by a number of factors including: a) the local environmental conditions; b) the raw materials used for the preparation (e.g., binder and aggregates) and the relative proportions, which also influence the pore network as well as the physical-mechanical properties of the mortar; and c) on-site construction practices [18].

The results highlighted that the dynamic interaction between humidity, water absorption, and salt crystallization is a primary driver of the long-term degradation of stone-based materials. The results of the aging protocols applied to both natural and artificial stones, as proposed in Deliverable D2.2, further highlight the strong interconnection among porosity, water absorption, and degradation [19, 20].

To optimize the conservation of stone-based artefacts, it is therefore essential to conduct tests both on untreated and treated samples, with hydrophobic, consolidating, and protective products [15, 21]. These treatments are widely employed in conservation to reduce water uptake, enhance cohesion, or limit surface deterioration; however, their performance can vary greatly depending on the type of stone, its porosity, mineralogical composition, and the specific environmental conditions to which it is exposed. Moreover, protective treatments may alter the water-transfer properties of the material, potentially leading to uneven moisture distribution, preferential salt accumulation, or

undesired changes in surface appearance over time. For this reason, assessing the hydric behavior and salt-crystallization resistance of treated samples is crucial to verify not only the immediate effectiveness of the products, but also their long-term compatibility, stability, and durability. Only through systematic testing on both untreated and treated geomaterials is it possible to identify the most suitable conservation strategies and to ensure that interventions do not inadvertently accelerate degradation processes [22, 23].

The monitoring procedure developed using IR spectroscopy, specifically attenuated total reflectance (FTIR-ATR), micro-transmission (μ -FTIR), and external reflection (ER-FTIR), has proven to be effective in assessing and controlling degradation processes. Data analysis through Principal Component Analysis (PCA) enabled faster interpretation of the spectral results, allowing the detection of even minimal variations in chemical composition and providing a detailed understanding of degradation patterns. The results demonstrated that the initial phase of natural stone degradation is influenced by seasonal cycles of water absorption and desorption, followed by the crystallization of salts.

The same behavior was observed for artificial materials, such as mortars, highlighting the importance of the variables identified more than the nature of the materials analyzed.

Based on the results described above the following **monitoring strategies and preventive conservation guidelines** are proposed:

- **evaluation of porosity** (both total open porosity and pore size distribution) in natural stone materials, which can be useful for predicting potential issues related to water absorption and salt crystallization;

- **monitoring water absorption** in natural and artificial stone materials using non-invasive and non-destructive techniques. IR spectroscopy, coupled with PCA analysis, can provide fast, reliable, and user-friendly support;
- **monitoring salt crystallization** through non-invasive and non-destructive techniques, which can assist in timely interventions and help prevent material loss and severe damage;
- **carrying out tests** not only on untreated materials per se, but also on those treated with hydrophobic agents, consolidants, and protective coatings.

Part of the results mentioned above appeared in two 2025 articles published in *GEM - International Journal on Geomathematics and Heritage*.

2.3 Metals (OPD: Galeotti M., Porcinai S., Brancolini T., Caruso O., Mugnaini S., Pieralli I.)

The research focuses on tarnishing of silver objects induced by sulfur-containing compounds. The most widespread prevention strategies used to protect silver cultural heritage from tarnishing involve the application of polymeric coatings. This project aims to quantitatively determine how the thickness of a protective coating influences the tarnishing rate of silver objects exposed to H₂S.

Previous phases of this research showed that the thickness of the polymeric film is a key parameter in protection against tarnishing, and that the tarnishing is controlled by the film thickness distribution on a micrometric scale. The effectiveness of different polymers at equal thickness has been compared and threshold thickness values have been defined below which protective efficacy is lost in the short or long term. All the previous experiments had been conducted under high RH % conditions (above 90%) (see Deliverable D2.1).

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In the final phases, the work focused on how polymer film thickness modulates the influence of environmental factors, such as RH % and UV irradiation, on the progression rate of H₂S-induced tarnishing. Many studies in literature examine silver tarnishing as environmental parameters vary, most of which focus on uncoated artefacts [24]. In practice, museum objects are either already coated from past interventions or expected to receive a protective coating, resulting in tarnishing behavior that is likely to differ from the theoretical models developed for uncoated objects. This research extends previous studies on the protective performance of silver coatings with varying environmental conditions, which do not examine the role of polymer film thickness in detail (*e.g.*, [25–30]).

19

Silver coupons coated with PB72 and Zapon (with different, accurately defined polymer film thicknesses) were **exposed to H₂S for further artificial aging experiments**, in particular:

(1) **one additional experiment at high RH % and two experiments at intermediate RH % (46-52%)** were performed or completed. The intermediate RH % values were achieved by placing a MgCl₂·6H₂O slurry inside the aging chamber. The experiments were preceded by calibration and fine-tuning of the aging system.

(2) **UVA-UVB irradiation experiments** were performed **before H₂S exposure**, to assess the effect of film thickness on irradiation-induced degradation of the polymer itself. 25×25 mm test samples were exposed to UV radiation on half of their surface. Irradiation conditions were the following:

- UVA: 864 h exposure, 0.68 W/m²/nm radiance (@340 nm), T = 20°C.

- UVB: 40 h exposure, 0.77 W/m²/nm radiance (@313 nm), T = 56°C.

(3) Repetition of intermediate-RH % test with a different H₂S supply rate, to evaluate how the aging protocol itself may influence the outcome.

20

The study identified, for different types of protective coating, the film-thickness ranges in which changes in environmental conditions produce large differences in H₂S-induced tarnishing, as well as those in which the effect of environmental variations on the tarnishing rate is negligible.

In the case of PB72, for short-intermediate experiment duration and with relatively thick films, protective efficacy was found to be highest at lower RH %. Considering average indoor H₂S concentrations of about 200 ppt, this behavior corresponds to an exposure E that could be reached in a museum environment over roughly 600–700 years. As thickness decreases and/or for longer duration, this trend reverses, with better performance at high RH %. Further investigations will explore these patterns. For Zapon, the strongest RH %-dependent differences in tarnishing rate occur at film thickness of about 10-15 μm, with improved protection at lower RH %. With higher or lower film thickness, RH % variations have little influence on tarnishing behavior (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Color variation (ΔE^*) with increasing H_2S exposure for a selection of samples. The thickness of the polymer film, as estimated by the EC test, is indicated.

In the aging tests preceded by UV pretreatment, PB72 treated coupons with film thickness around $20 \mu m$ showed the greatest discrepancy in tarnishing rate between UV-pretreated and non-pretreated specimens. In this range, UV irradiation improved protective performance (possibly due to cross-linking phenomena that reduced film permeability). For samples with thicker or thinner polymeric films, UV pretreatment had no significant effect on the

tarnishing rate (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Color variation with increasing H₂S exposure for a selection of PB72-coated samples after UV pretreatment (blue lines), compared with no UV pretreated samples (red lines).

For Zapon, the same UV pretreatment caused strong damage to the polymer film, forcing the experiment to be stopped at low H₂S exposures. The discrepancy in tarnishing rate between UV pretreated and non-pretreated samples increased as film thickness decreased. No significant differences were observed in the outcomes as a function of the H₂S supply rate (assuming the same final exposure, which reached about 115 ppm/day in 40 or 25 days). In any case, these tests represent an extreme acceleration compared with what may occur in an actual museum environment. Accordingly, the following indications are intended as a general guidance in the spirit of the precautionary principle.

Evaluating the thickness and homogeneity of the protective coating after application is essential for long-term protection effectiveness. This can be done qualitatively with UV fluorescence imaging and quantitatively using Eddy Current testing, MA-XRF scanning, or transreflection FTIR, based on the geometry and dimension of the object. The application thickness should balance protective performance with minimal aesthetic impact assessed via color measurement, ensuring that the ΔE^* remains below 2.5.

Based on the results obtained in the various tests (see also Deliverable D2.1), the film thickness values reported in Table 1 can be recommended.

Table 1. Recommended protective film thickness for silver objects.

	Silver coated with PB72	Silver coated with Zapon
Polymer film thickness	15-25 µm	At least 10 µm, preferably more, as long as the aesthetic impact of the application remains minimal

Tests were carried out on two specific coatings, PB72 and Zapon, which exhibited very different behaviors; therefore, these data cannot be extended to other categories of protective coatings, for which dedicated testing would be required. The intrinsic protective effectiveness of PB72 against H₂S-induced tarnishing proved to be lower than Zapon' one and cannot be compensated by further increasing the film thickness. **Therefore, Zapon remains the recommended option between the two coatings, provided that adequate UV protection can be ensured.**

The experiments showed that **the behavior of different polymers changes with varying RH %**. However, within the recommended thickness ranges indicated above, the typical RH % values suggested by museum-environment guidelines [31] can be considered optimal over long timescales. Regarding UV irradiation, although possible cross-linking phenomena can produce partially positive results for PB72, **it remains advisable to minimize this external degradation factor for polymer films.**

It is recommended to carry out periodic colorimetric tests on the silver object (preferably every 10 years), ensuring that the ΔE* remains below 2.5.

2.4 Works on paper/biodeterioration (UNINA: Birolo L., Pizzimenti S., Pollio A., Sannino M. F., Vergara A.; UNIBO: Prati S., Sciutto G., Gatti L.)

A detailed investigation into biodeteriogens affecting paper-based heritage materials was conducted with the aim of identifying the main risk factors responsible for early degradation phenomena. Fungi were confirmed as the primary agents of concern, especially in environments characterized by fluctuating humidity and limited air circulation—conditions commonly observed in archives, libraries and museum storage areas. Addressing these risks is crucial, as fungal colonization often begins at the microscopic level, long before visible damage (such as staining, weakening of fibers or surface powdering) becomes detectable through conventional visual inspection.

Within this framework, the activities carried out were aimed at verifying the possibility to adopt a **set of tools and methodologies as early detection methods**:

a) IRIS system in the VIS–NIR region (UNIBO). IRIS was used to map mock-ups paper inoculated with *Cladosporium cladosporoides* the same day and then each 24 hours. Thanks to chemometric data processing, it was possible to distinguish the area of biodeteriogen growth from the still safe paper. Even if this approach should still be tested on different microorganisms and type of paper, according to these preliminary results, the use of **VIS–NIR imaging as a non-invasive monitoring tool could help in the identification of early chemical and optical changes in paper fibers** that may indicate the onset of biodeterioration. In real collection environments, this approach enables curators and conservators to **localize early fungal growth before it becomes**

visible, compare the condition of multiple items within a collection rapidly, track the progression or stabilization of degradation after changes in environmental management, document the condition of highly fragile objects without requiring physical contact.

This is particularly valuable for large archival collections, where periodic routine checks must be both time-efficient and non-invasive.

b) Immunochemical protocols (UNIBO). An immunochemical protocol has been designed to detect the **presence of cellulase activity** (sensitivity 0.5 µg/mL), which delivers a **direct measure of enzymatic threats to cellulose, even before structural weakening becomes measurable.**

The test has been developed first on the standard enzyme and then on standard paper, inoculated with *Cladosporium cladosporoides* evaluating the production of cellulase sampling the colonized surface with different approaches: nitrocellulose, swabs, electrospun materials, to improve the efficiency and safety of collecting residue or microbial traces from fragile documents. Then the cells were separated from the sampling material and spotted on nitrocellulose support. The immunochemical protocol involves the subsequent treatment of the membranes with a blocking solution to avoid aspecific interactions, primary antigen specific antibody and secondary specie-specific antibody horseradish peroxidase (HRP) labelled antibody. After the addition of the HRP-substrate signal is present only if the enzyme is present.

The capability to measure enzyme presence and activity before visible damage is crucial in cases where the object shows no visible symptoms yet but may be

undergoing silent biochemical degradation. Moreover, the possibility to improve the sampling efficiency is especially relevant in real case studies involving highly brittle or chemically unstable papers, items where sampling must be strictly minimal (e.g., works of high artistic or historical value), complex stratified materials such as manuscripts with ink layers sensitive to touch.

Experiments performed on standard mock-ups are an important starting point suggesting that the proposed approach could be adopted as reliable diagnostic tool. The combined use of hyperspectral monitoring and of the biochemical assay offers an operational framework adaptable to routine practice in archives and museums, contributing to more informed decision-making and more effective preventive conservation policies.

c) Chemical and colorimetric investigation on paper-ink mock-ups (UNINA). This research activity was focused also on poorly investigated, though potentially very common inks: mixed carbon-iron gall inks.

Carbon-based inks produced by mixing soot or charcoal with a binder, usually arabic gum, have been used since Antiquity. Iron-gall inks (IGI), obtained by the reaction of iron sulfate with gallnut extracts, were, instead, the most used inks during the Middle Ages and up to the 20th century. Although mixed carbon-iron-based inks have also been mentioned in literature, their degradation processes remain largely unexplored.

As relevant case study, a combination of non-destructive (ATR-FTIR and Raman micro-spectroscopy) and micro-destructive (GC-MS and HPLC-MS) diagnostic methods have been used to characterize the ink used in Luigi Vanvitelli's

correspondence stored in the Royal Palace of Caserta. Recent studies on the manuscripts revealed the use of a **mixed Carbon-Iron Gall ink raising some degradation issues**.

27

Therefore, this research activity dealt with the preparation of different ink mock-ups, containing combinations of iron sulfate, gallic acid, carbon black, arabic gum, applied to two different supports, namely glass and paper. These mock-ups were characterized by a chemical and colorimetric point of view before and after an artificial thermal aging, conducted at controlled temperature (80 °C) and humidity (65 %), to identify the ink degradation products, thus, to propose a chemical degradation mechanism of the ink.

In the end, **carbon black addition was found to accelerate the degradation of the ink via two main processes**: carbon black can both absorb gallic acid-related species, thereby destroying the pigment Fe (III)-gallate complex, and accelerate the oxidation of gallic acid to ellagic acid. Moreover, because of poor gallic acid detectability, **it is hard to distinguish thermally aged carbon-containing iron-gall ink (C-IGI) from traditional carbon-based inks via non-invasive spectroscopic techniques** (such as Raman spectroscopy), implying that **destructive more sensitive analytical techniques (such as HPLC) are required** for the reliable characterization of ancient inks.

The **colorimetric data analysis** carried out at the Dept. of Industrial Engineering of UNINA has well integrated the chemical diagnostic approach, since this analysis is often the first investigation used by restorers to assess the state of conservation of ancient manuscripts. Indeed, the ink mock-ups are affected

by color variations both immediately after being applied to paper and being preserved in environmental conditions (these variations stabilize after 4 weeks) and after aging. Focusing on the effect of the aging process **colorimetric analysis allows for a quantification of the observed chromatic variations**: a) mock-ups without carbon show a less pronounced color change (Fig. 4); b) carbon-IGI mock-ups are lighter than IGI even before the aging (if comparing in pairs samples with arabic gum and without arabic gum), and carbon-containing inks become even lighter during the aging (higher variations of lightness; see Fig. 5); c) both IGI and C-IGI initially have a blue-violet appearance (hue ranging from 210° and 310°) and they get brownish upon aging (hue ranging from 48° to 73°): both IGI and C-IGI exhibit a high hue variation after only one day of aging; d) IGI mock-ups initially exhibit very low chroma (below 1.9) and become more saturated during the aging (variation ranging from 1.2 and 14.3). Conversely, C-IGI mock-ups have a slightly higher initial chroma (ranging from 4.1 and 5.5) and immediately lose colorfulness during the first day (except for one case), concurrently with the hue variation; subsequently, they exhibit a significant increase in chroma during the remainder of the aging period reaching chrome values between 14.9 and 18.9.

Regarding **preventive conservation guidelines**, from our investigation, the **carbon presence found in Middle age-19th century inks should alert on its potential destructive effect in mixed carbon-iron gall inks, with colorimetric analysis well translated into chemical modifications of the C-IGI upon aging.**

Figure 4. Colorimetric variations (ΔE^*_{ab}) under D65 illuminant obtained comparing data at the end of the experiment with those measured before aging.

Figure 5. Colorimetric coordinates under D65 illuminant (Lightness -L-, Hue -h- and Chroma -C-) during aging process. Numbers on graphs represent the differences calculated comparing data at the end of the experiment with those measured before the aging

3. Conclusions

In this deliverable, a solid framework of analytical monitoring methodologies is designed to track degradation pathways and refine preventive conservation guidelines for the cultural heritage objects studied.

By investigating a wide range of materials, ranging from pigments and dyes in paint and textiles to stone, silver, and paper-based substrates, the research provides a comprehensive view of material degradation.

The findings synthesized in Tables 2–5 provide a critical evaluation of the experimental results, establishing a technical foundation to refine future conservation strategies and risk assessment models.

Table 2. Summary of the analyzed paint and textile samples with corresponding key-degradation factors, main alteration compounds, analytical strategy for monitoring degradation and recommendations for preventive conservation guidelines (cfr. par. 2.1).

Sample	Key degradation factors	Main alteration compounds	Analytical strategy for monitoring degradation	Recommendations for preventive conservation guidelines	Partners involved
Arsenic-based pigments					
Orpiment oil/egg/arabic gum paints	Darkness, T= 40°C, RH %=89%, pH= 8	Arsenolite, Elemental sulfur	Micro-XRF, MAXRD, 3D CXRF	Accurately assess the RH % and pH levels to which objects are exposed, avoiding high levels of RH % and keeping neutral to slightly acidic pH	CNR- ISPC,
Realgar oil/egg/arabic gum paints	Darkness, T= 40°C, RH %=89%, pH= 8	Arsenolite, Elemental sulfur, As-S polymorphs	Micro-XRF, MAXRD, 3D CXRF	Accurately assess the RH % and pH levels to which objects are exposed, avoiding high levels of RH % and keeping neutral to slightly acidic pH	CNR- ISPC
Orpiment and realgar gum/alkyd resin	Darkness, environmental T and RH %	Arsenolite	As K-/S K-edges XAS and FTIR spectroscopy	Accurately define the nature of the binding medium	CNR- SCITEC, UNIBO
Orpiment and realgar oil		Arsenic (V) and sulfates			
Emerald green	UVA-VIS light	Arsenic (V)	As K-edge XAS and ER-FTIR spectroscopy	RH %<50%; light exposure optimized for sensitive pigments[32]; lighting selection/adjustments based on the VIS absorption properties of emerald green	CNR- SCITEC
	Darkness, T= 40°C, RH %≥95%	Arsenolite			
Lead-based pigments					
Cerussite	Darkness, T=25°C, RH %=81%, pH= 6	Plattnerite, scrutinyite	MAXRD	Accurately assess the RH % and pH levels to which objects are exposed	CNR- ISPC
Cobalt-based pigments					
Smalt	Darkness, T= 25°C, RH %=94%, pH= 8	Potassium Leaching, silica network etching	Micro-XRF, MAXRD, 3D CXRF	Accurately assess the RH % and pH levels to which objects are exposed, avoiding high levels of RH % and keeping neutral to slightly acidic pH	CNR- ISPC
Silver gilding	Darkness, T= 40°C, RH %=89%, pH= 8	Silver oxide, chlorargyrite, smithite	Micro-XRF, MAXRD	Accurately assess the RH % and pH levels to which objects are exposed, avoiding high levels of RH % and keeping neutral to slightly acidic pH	CNR- ISPC
Sulfide-based pigments					
Cadmium yellows	UVA-VIS light and RH %≥95%	Cadmium sulfates	S K-edge XANES imaging and ER-FTIR spectroscopy	Storage in RH %<50%; light exposure for lightfast pigments[32]	CNR- SCITEC, CNR-IAC
Triarylmethane dyes (TAMs)					
TAMs	UVA-VIS light	N-dealkylation and oxidative degradation with benzophenone derivatives formation	UV–VIS–NIR and Surface Enhanced Raman spectroscopy	Light exposure optimized for sensitive dyes [32]; lighting selection/adjustments based on the VIS absorption properties of TAMs	CNR- SCITEC

Table 3. Summary of the analyzed stone samples with corresponding key-degradation factors, main alteration compounds, analytical strategy for monitoring degradation and recommendations for preventive conservation guidelines (cfr. par. 2.2).

Sample	Key degradation factors	Main alteration compounds	Analytical strategy for monitoring degradation	Recommendations for preventive conservation guidelines	Partners involved
limestone	Water, $\Delta T > 10$ °C	salts	ER-FTIR spectroscopy, evaluation of porosity (both total open porosity and pore size distribution), salt crystallization test (ER-FTIR, Raman spectroscopy)	1. monitoring water absorption 2. monitoring salt crystallization 3. tests on both untreated and treated (with hydrophobic, consolidating, and protective products) materials	UNICT, UNIROMA1
white marbles	Water, $\Delta T > 10$ °C			Tests on both untreated and treated (with hydrophobic, consolidating, and protective products) materials	
travertine	Water, $\Delta T > 10$ °C			1. monitoring water absorption 2. monitoring salt crystallization 3. tests on both untreated and treated (with hydrophobic, consolidating, and protective products) materials	
wackestone	Water, $\Delta T > 10$ °C			Tests on both untreated and treated (with hydrophobic, consolidating, and protective products) materials	
quartz sand lime mortar	Water, $\Delta T > 10$ °C, nature of binder ad aggregate			1. monitoring water absorption 2. monitoring salt crystallization 3. tests on both untreated and treated (with hydrophobic, consolidating, and protective products) materials	
volcanic sand lime mortar	Water, $\Delta T > 10$ °C, nature of binder ad aggregate			1. monitoring water absorption 2. monitoring salt crystallization 3. tests on both untreated and treated (with hydrophobic, consolidating, and protective products) materials	

Table 4. Summary of the analyzed silver mock-ups with corresponding key-degradation factors, main alteration compounds, analytical strategy for monitoring degradation and recommendations for preventive conservation guidelines (cfr. par. 2.3).

Mock-ups	Key degradation factors	Main alteration compounds	Analytical strategy for monitoring degradation	Recommendations for preventive conservation guidelines	Partners involved
Sterling silver protected with Paraloid B72	H ₂ S, High RH %	Ag ₂ S	Colorimetry	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Check the thickness of protective film 2. monitoring color changes 3. Application of films with a 15-25 µm thickness 4. Keep RH % in the 40-60% range 	OPD
Sterling silver protected with Zapon	H ₂ S, High RH %	Ag ₂ S	Colorimetry	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Check the thickness of protective film 2. monitoring color changes 3. Application of films with a thickness of at least 10 µm, preferably more, as long as the aesthetic impact of the film remains minimal 4. Keep RH % in the range 40-60% 5. Avoid exposure to UV radiation 	OPD

Table 5. Summary of the analyzed paper-based samples with corresponding key-degradation factors, main alteration compounds, analytical strategy for monitoring degradation and recommendations for preventive conservation guidelines (cfr. par. 2.4).

Samples	Key degradation factors	Main alteration compounds	Analytical strategy for monitoring degradation	Recommendations for preventive conservation guidelines	Partners involved
Paper-ink mock-ups on paper or glass supports: iron sulfate/ gallic acid/carbon black/ Arabic arabic gum	Darkness, T= 80°C, RH %=65%	Ellagic acid, iron-altered polyphenol complexes	GC-MS, HPLC-MS, IR and Raman spectroscopy, colorimetry	Non-invasive spectroscopies (e.g., Raman s.) should not be used alone to identify mixed carbon- iron-gall inks. When carbon is detected, complementary chromatographic analysis (e.g., HPLC-MS) is required to ensure reliable identification. Manuscripts containing mixed carbon-iron-gall inks should be classified as high risk due to accelerated chemical degradation and significant colorimetric instability.	UNINA
Paper mock-ups with <i>Cladosporium cladosporioides</i> growth	RH %	Cellulase, colony growth	Immuno-sensor, IRIS system (vis-NIR imaging)	Define "alert zones" by correlating spectral signatures and chemometric signal with quantitative microbiological indicators. This allows for the detection of risks before they are visible to the human eye and justifies precise adjustments to microclimates.	UNIBO

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Annex A. List of research products of WP2

a) Peer review articles, book chapters, conference proceedings (with doi), pre-prints

40

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- 18) Capozzi, F., Sorrentino, M. C., Granata, A., Vergara, A., Alberico, M., Rossi, M., Spagnuolo, V., Giordano, S. (2023). Optimizing moss and lichen transplants as biomonitors of airborne anthropogenic microfibers. *Biology*, 12, 1278. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biology12101278>

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- 19) Lemorini C., Masi A., Medeghini L., Sadori L., Cerafogli E., Di Fazio M., Previti G., 2025. Pietra, malta e legno nel patrimonio architettonico: una proposta di analisi multidisciplinare. In: MATERIALI E STRUTTURE. - ISSN 1121-2373. - Nuova serie - anno XIV:27-28 (2025), pp. 31-48.
- 20) Di Fazio M., Calzolari L., Capriotti S., Rea C., Medeghini L. (2025). Integrated IR Multi-Methods Protocol for Cultural Heritage Geomaterials: Evaluation of Statistical Data Processing, Volume 101 of the Springer Proceedings in Materials series "Advances in Nondestructive Evaluation Technologies for the Preservation of Cultural Heritage" 2025.

42

b) Conferences

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- 1) Pezzella M. et al. (2026). Mathematical Modeling for Heritage Science: Predictive Frameworks for Conservation and Safeguarding, 14-16/01/2026, Roma (Italia), Convegno finale CHANGES: Mappe e scenari per il futuro del patrimonio culturale. Tre anni di ricerche del partenariato PNRR CHANGES (oral presentation).
- 2) Bretti G. et al. (2025). La modellistica matematica al servizio delle scienze del patrimonio culturale: strumenti predittivi per conservazione e salvaguardia sostenibili, 11/12/2025, Roma (Italia), DIITET Conference (oral presentation).
- 3) Bretti G. et al. (2025). Mathematical modelling of water absorption properties for historical lime-based mortars, 06/10/2025, Roma (Italia), Math4Cult - Mathematical tools for Cultural Heritage Conference (oral presentation).
- 4) Pezzella M. et al. (2025). Predictive Modeling of Cadmium Yellow Fading via X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy-Calibrated Integro-Differential Approaches, 06/10/2025, Roma (Italia), Math4Cult - Mathematical tools for Cultural Heritage Conference (oral presentation).
- 5) Pezzella M. et al. (2025). Structure-preserving Numerical Methods for Non-local Photochemical Kinetics, 26/06/2025, Roma (Italia), International Workshop on Modern Problems of Analysis, Optimization, Approximation and Their Applications (oral presentation).
- 6) Pezzella M. et al. (2025). Photocatalytic Degradation of Cadmium Pigments: Integro-Differential Modeling and Positivity Preserving Numerical Methods, 15/05/2025, Salerno (Italia), III Meeting ANA&A – SIMAI. (oral presentation).
- 7) Pezzella M. et al. (2025). Predicting Cadmium Pigments Degradation in Cultural Heritage: A Comprehensive Mathematical and Computational Framework, 7/05/2025, Perugia (Italia), TECHNART2025 Conference. (oral presentation).
- 8) Pezzella M. et al. (2025). Mathematical and Numerical Modeling of Photochemical Degradation in Pictorial Matrices, 20/01/2025, Napoli (Italia), DSABSN2025 - 17th International conference on dynamical systems applied to biology and natural sciences. (oral presentation).

CNR-ISPC

- 9) Arcidiacono et al. (2026). Detecting Pigment Degradation in Artworks with Laboratory XAS: A Step Toward Synchrotron-Level Analysis 14-16/01/2026, Roma (Italia), Convegno finale CHANGES: Mappe e scenari per il futuro del patrimonio culturale. Tre anni di ricerche del partenariato PNRR CHANGES (poster presentation).
- 10) Barba Castagnaro I. (2026) et al., Microtomography, μ Raman, and Multimodal Analysis of Swords from Torre Galli Tombs at the Archaeological Museum of Reggio Calabria (MarRC), 14-16/01/2026, Roma (Italia), Convegno finale CHANGES: Mappe e scenari per il futuro del patrimonio culturale. Tre anni di ricerche del partenariato PNRR CHANGES (oral presentation).

- 11) Caliri C. et al. (2026). Advanced X-ray-driven diagnostics for the noninvasive characterization of painting stratigraphies, 14-16/01/2026, Roma (Italia), Convegno finale CHANGES: Mappe e scenari per il futuro del patrimonio culturale. Tre anni di ricerche del partenariato PNRR CHANGES (oral presentation).
- 12) Falcone F. et al. (2026). A robotic spectrometer for 3D, non-invasive MA-XRF analysis of Cultural Heritage artifacts: case study applications, 14-16/01/2026, Roma (Italia), Convegno finale CHANGES: Mappe e scenari per il futuro del patrimonio culturale. Tre anni di ricerche del partenariato PNRR CHANGES (poster presentation).
- 13) Ravan E.L. et al. (2026). Investigating sulfur crystal formation in arsenic sulfide pigments by using advanced mobile X-rays methods, 14-16/01/2026, Roma (Italia), Convegno finale CHANGES: Mappe e scenari per il futuro del patrimonio culturale. Tre anni di ricerche del partenariato PNRR CHANGES (poster presentation).
- 14) Romano F.P. et al. (2026). Science and Technology for Sustainable Diagnostics of Cultural Heritage, Convegno finale CHANGES: Mappe e scenari per il futuro del patrimonio culturale. Tre anni di ricerche del partenariato PNRR CHANGES (oral presentation).
- 15) Barba Castagnaro, I. et al. (2025). Microtomography, μ Raman, and Multimodal Analysis of Swords from Torre Galli Tombs at the Archaeological Museum of Reggio Calabria (MarRC), 28–30/10/2025, Catania (Italy), Workshop CHANGES SPOKE 5 (oral presentation).
- 16) Ravan E.L. et al. (2025). Investigating sulfur crystal formation in arsenic sulfide pigments by using advanced mobile x-rays methods, 28–30/10/2025, Catania (Italy), Workshop CHANGES SPOKE 5 (oral presentation).
- 17) Romano F.P. et al. (2025). A robotic multimodal Spectrometer for noninvasive in situ analysis of 3D heritage objects, 28–30/10/2025, Catania (Italy), Workshop CHANGES SPOKE 5 (oral presentation).
- 18) Tapia J. et al. (2025), Mobile 3D Confocal XRF, combined with AR-XRF and synchrotron nano-XRF, for the non-invasive 3D elemental analysis of heterogeneous artworks, 28–30/10/2025, Catania (Italy), Workshop CHANGES SPOKE 5 (oral presentation).
- 19) Caliri et al. (2025). The three Margarito paintings at the Museo Nazionale d'Arte Medievale e Moderna, Arezzo: multi analytical technique non-invasive study, 9-11/10/2025, Arezzo (Italy), DUECENTO painting: the art and technique of Margarito d'Arezzo and his contemporaries (oral presentation).
- 20) Falcone F. et al. (2025). Non-invasive analysis of Egyptian wooden funerary stelae by MA-XRF and MA-XRD: an interdisciplinary study on materials and technology, 22–26/09/2025, Palermo (Italy), 111° Congresso Nazionale della Società Italiana di Fisica.
- 21) Caliri et al. (2025). Le tecniche di Imaging di fluorescenza e diffrazione a raggi X dell'infrastruttura E-RIHS nello studio della Venere di Botticelli dei Musei Reali di Torino, 25/09/2025, Turin (Italy), Oltre la bellezza, ricerche sulla Venere di Botticelli (oral presentation).
- 22) Ravan E.L. et al. (2025). Investigating sulfur crystal formation in arsenic sulfide pigments by using advanced mobile x-rays methods, 19–20/06/2025, Catania (Italy), ISA2025 (oral presentation).
- 23) Caliri C. et al. (2025). Analisi dei materiali e tecnica pittorica nei dipinti di Solario del Museo Poldi Pezzoli, 13/05/2025, Milan (Italy), Tra tecnica e arte: indagini su Andrea Solario (oral presentation).
- 24) Andolina R. et al. (2025). Classification of Egyptian funerary nets from MA-XRF, 6-9/05/2025, Perugia (Italy), TECHNART 2025 (poster presentation).

- 25) Botticelli M. et al. Copper arsenate greens in ancient art: advanced mobile and lab-based X-ray methods for re-defining the palette of macedonian funerary painting (2025). 6-9/05/2025, Perugia (Italy), TECHNART 2025 (oral presentation).
- 26) Caliri C. et al. (2025). Advancing micro-XRF imaging: a novel full-field approach for high-resolution elemental mapping in heritage science, 6-9/05/2025, Perugia (Italy), TECHNART 2025 (poster presentation).
- 27) Falcone F. et al. (2025). Non-invasive MA-XRPD and MA-XRF analysis of Egyptian wooden funerary stelae from the Hellenic National Archaeological Museum Poster, 6-9/05/2025, Perugia (Italy), TECHNART 2025 (poster presentation).
- 28) Longo S. et al. (2025). The doors of the Basilica di San Marco: a scientific examination through MA-XRF, 6-9/05/2025, Perugia (Italy), TECHNART 2025 (poster presentation).
- 29) Preisler Z. et al. (2025). Advances in deep learning for multimodal XRF/XRD analysis for cultural heritage, 6-9/05/2025, Perugia (Italy), TECHNART 2025 (oral presentation).
- 30) Ravan E.L. et al. (2025). Investigating sulfur crystal formation in arsenic sulfide pigments by using advanced mobile X-rays methods, 6-9/05/2025, Perugia (Italy), TECHNART 2025 (oral presentation).
- 31) Ravan E.L. et al. (2025). Illegible writings recovered in carbonized fire damaged manuscripts with high lateral resolution and high chemical sensitivity μ -XRF scanning: the case of the torino, bnu, l.ii.14., 6-9/05/2025, Perugia (Italy), TECHNART 2025 (poster presentation).
- 32) Romano F.P. et al. (2025). A robotic multimodal XRF-IR spectrometer for noninvasive in situ analysis of 3D heritage objects, 6-9/05/2025, Perugia (Italy), TECHNART 2025 (poster presentation).
- 33) Santagati G. et al. (2025). Lab-based XAS spectroscopy in the study of pigment materials serving the FIXLAB platform of E-RIHS, 6-9/05/2025, Perugia (Italy), TECHNART 2025 (poster presentation).
- 34) Tapia J. et al. (2025). Confocal and angular-resolved XRF: a comparative study of mobile techniques for the non-invasive analysis of layered structures in artworks, 6-9/05/2025, Perugia (Italy), TECHNART 2025 (oral presentation).
- 35) Caliri C. et al. (2025). Discovering a textual layout in the unrolled carbonised papyri from Herculaneum using a novel mobile highly sensitive MA-XRF Imaging technique, 14/04/2025, Barcelona (Spain), From Fibre to Script: Scientific Approaches to Unraveling the Material Culture of Ancient Papyrus Manuscripts (invited oral presentation).
- 36) Romano F.P. et al. (2025). Advanced X-ray technologies for the non-invasive and in situ characterisation of ancient papyri, 14/04/2025, Barcelona (Spain), From Fibre to Script: Scientific Approaches to Unraveling the Material Culture of Ancient Papyrus Manuscripts (invited oral presentation).
- 37) Botticelli M. et al. (2025). Revisualizing the artists' palette in the Hunt frieze of the tomb of Philip II at Vergina through the MOLAB in situ investigation, 05/04/2025, Athens (Greece), ReVis International Workshop "The Aigai Hunt Frieze Revealed" (oral presentation).
- 38) Caliri C. et al. (2025). XRAYLab: Innovating Mobile X-ray Technologies for Tangible Cultural Heritage Analysis, 05/04/2025, Athens (Greece), ReVis International Workshop "The Aigai Hunt Frieze Revealed" (oral presentation).
- 39) Botticelli M. et al. (2025). A rediscovery of Macedonian artists' rich palette: the in-situ investigation of the Hunt frieze of the tomb of Philip II at Aigai (Vergina, Greece), 12-14/02/2025, Palermo (Italy), XIII Congresso Nazionale AIAR (poster presentation).

- 40) Caliri C. et al. (2025). Novel X-ray imaging techniques for the non-invasive investigation of European Heritage within MOLAB platform of E-RIHS, 12-14/02/2025, Palermo (Italy), XIII Congresso Nazionale AIAr (poster presentation).
- 41) Longo S. et al. (2025). Combined Macro-XRF and X-ray radiography analysis of Renaissance masterpieces. 12-14/02/2025, Palermo (Italy), XIII Congresso Nazionale AIAr (oral presentation).
- 42) Ravan E.L. et al. (2025). Egyptian Blue: variability in production technology, material provenance and deterioration, 12-14/02/2025, Palermo (Italy), XIII Congresso Nazionale AIAr (oral presentation).
- 43) Ravan E.L. et al. (2025). Advanced X-ray methods for the non-invasive investigation of pigment degradation, 23-24/01/2025, Rome (Italy), Convegno CHANGES "Patrimonio culturale al futuro: sostenibilità sociale, innovazione tecnologica, trasformazione digitale. Le ricerche in corso nel Progetto CHANGES" (poster presentation).
- 44) Romano F.P. et al. (2025). Integrated analytical technologies and artificial intelligence for advancing knowledge and conservation of tangible Cultural Heritage, 23-24/01/2025, Rome (Italy), Convegno CHANGES "Patrimonio culturale al futuro: sostenibilità sociale, innovazione tecnologica, trasformazione digitale. Le ricerche in corso nel Progetto CHANGES" (oral presentation).
- 45) Marketou A.K. et al. (2024), Tracing the trajectories of Egyptian blue production technology: XRD, sXRF and sXANES analysis of Hellenistic and Roman samples, 27-31/08/2024, Rome (Italy), 30th Annual Meeting of the European Association of Archaeologists (EAA) (oral presentation).
- 46) Liggins F. et al. (2024), Understanding the Carolingian artist through a novel workflow involving multimodal remote and in-situ spectral imaging and spectroscopic techniques, 27-31/08/2024, Rome (Italy), 30th Annual Meeting of the European Association of Archaeologists (EAA) (oral presentation).
- 47) Preisler Z. et al. (2024), Deep learning for MA-XRD/MA-XRF imaging for pigment-specific analysis of paintings, 07-12/07/2024, Les Diablerets (Swiss), GRC - Gordon Research Conference (poster presentation).
- 48) Ravan E.L. et al. (2024), Egyptian Blue in Macedonian paintings: materials, technology and provenance investigated by using X-ray techniques, 07-12/07/2024, Les Diablerets (Swiss), GRC - Gordon Research Conference (poster presentation).
- 49) Romano F.P. (2024), Enhancing Data Interpretation in Non-invasive Investigations of Artworks: Combining Advanced X-Ray Imaging Methods and Machine Learning, 07-12/07/2024, Les Diablerets (Swiss), GRC - Gordon Research Conference (oral presentation).
- 50) Caliri C. et al. (2024), Novel X-ray imaging techniques for the noninvasive investigation of European Heritage within MOLAB platform of E-RIHS, 24-28/06/2024, Athens (Greece), EXRS2024, (oral lecture).
- 51) Marketou A.K. et al. (2024), On the production of Egyptian blue: sXRF and XANES analysis of pigment pellets, 24-28/06/2024, Athens (Greece), EXRS2024 (oral presentation).
- 52) Ravan E.L. et al. (2024), Egyptian Blue: variability in production technology, material provenance and deterioration, 24-28/06/2024, Athens (Greece), EXRS2024 (oral presentation).
- 53) Botticelli M. et al. (2024), The MOLAB transnational access for an in-situ investigation of the Hunt frieze of the tomb of Philip II at Aigai (Vergina, Greece), 04-07/06/2024, Washington (USA), X-ray fluorescence imaging (MA-XRF) and reflectance imaging spectroscopy (RIS) meeting (oral presentation).

- 54) Preisler Z. et al. (2024), Deep Learning Applications for MA-XRF Imaging, 04-07/06/2024, Washington (USA), X-ray fluorescence imaging (MA-XRF) and reflectance imaging spectroscopy (RIS) meeting (oral presentation).
- 55) Caliri C. et al. (2023), Discovering a textual layout in the unrolled carbonized papyri from Herculaneum by the new highly sensitive MA-XRF scanner developed at ISPC-CNR, 11-15/09/2023, Salerno (Italy), 109° CONGRESSO NAZIONALE Società Italiana di Fisica (oral presentation).
- 56) Preisler Z. et al. (2023), Deep learning models for MA-XRF imaging of paintings. 11-15/09/2023, Salerno (Italy), 109° CONGRESSO NAZIONALE Società Italiana di Fisica (oral presentation).

46

CNR-SCITEC

- 57) Mattana S. et al. (2026). From multi-scale spectroscopy to model calibration: experimental parameters to monitor and predict the photo-oxidation of cadmium yellow in oil paintings, 14-16/01/2026, Roma (Italia), Convegno finale CHANGES: Mappe e scenari per il futuro del patrimonio culturale. Tre anni di ricerche del partenariato PNRR CHANGES (oral presentation).
- 58) Pinto C. et al. (2026). Spectroscopic Approaches for Understanding Colorant Stability in Heritage Textiles, 14-16/01/2026, Roma (Italia), Convegno finale CHANGES: Mappe e scenari per il futuro del patrimonio culturale. Tre anni di ricerche del partenariato PNRR CHANGES (oral presentation).
- 59) Costantino C. et al. (2026). From research to impact: scaling Science Communication methodology across paintings materials, 14-16/01/2026, Roma (Italia), Convegno finale CHANGES: Mappe e scenari per il futuro del patrimonio culturale. Tre anni di ricerche del partenariato PNRR CHANGES (poster presentation).
- 60) Monico L. et al. (2025). Chemical stability of arsenic-based yellow and green paints: the role of the oil binder and environmental factors, 28-30/10/2025, Catania (Italia), Sustainable Diagnostics and Cultural Heritage. Achievements and Perspectives of CHANGES Spoke 5 (oral presentation).
- 61) Mattana S. et al. (2025). From Experimental Spectroscopy to Mathematical Modeling: Quantitative Insights into the Photo-Oxidative Degradation of Cadmium Yellow paints, 28-30/10/2025, Catania (Italia), Sustainable Diagnostics and Cultural Heritage. Achievements and Perspectives of CHANGES Spoke 5 (oral presentation)
- 62) Pinto C. et al. (2025). Spectroscopic Insights into the Triarylmethane Dyes, 28-30/10/2025, Catania (Italia), Sustainable Diagnostics and Cultural Heritage. Achievements and Perspectives of CHANGES Spoke 5 (oral presentation).
- 63) Monico L. et al. (2025). Probing the alteration processes of arsenic- and iron-based pigments in oil paintings: a multi-technique study at multiple length scales, 6-8/10/2025, Roma (Italia), Workshop "Mathematical tools for Cultural Heritage", Workshop "Mathematical tools for Cultural Heritage" (oral presentation).
- 64) Mattana S. et al. (2025). From Experimental Spectroscopy to Mathematical Modeling: Quantitative Insights into the Photo-Oxidative Degradation of Cadmium Yellow paints, - 8/10/2025, Roma (Italia), Workshop "Mathematical tools for Cultural Heritage", Workshop "Mathematical tools for Cultural Heritage" (oral presentation).
- 65) Costantino C. et al. (2025). Dalla provetta al like, come si costruisce una comunicazione che funziona?, 21/09/2025–25/09/2025, XLII Convegno Nazionale della Divisione di Chimica Organica (CDCO 2025), Villasimius, Cagliari (Italia) (oral presentation).

- 66) Pinto C. et al. (2025). Triarylmethane Dyes on a 19th Century Cotton Dress: non-invasive and micro-invasive strategies for digital heritage reconstruction, 10/09/2025–13/09/2025, XXI Congresso Nazionale della Divisione di Chimica dell'Ambiente e dei Beni Culturali, Società Chimica Italiana, Cremona (Italia) (oral presentation).
- 67) Pinto C. et al. (2025). Exploring the Photodegradation of Purple Textiles via SERS and Steady State Spectroscopy, 3-6/09/2025, International Conference on the Application of Raman Spectroscopy in Art and Archaeology and School, RAA, Pisa (Italia) (oral presentation).
- 68) Carboni Marri S. et al. (2025). Extrinsic and intrinsic factors affecting the alteration of emerald green in 19th–20th century oil paintings: the role of paint composition and environmental conditions, 6-9/05/2025, TECHNART 2025, Perugia (Italia) (oral presentation).
- 69) Pinto C. et al. (2025). Tracing fading colours: Analytical insights into a Historic Calico-Printed Cotton Dress, 6-9/05/2025, TECHNART 2025, Perugia (Italia) (oral presentation).
- 70) Mattana S. et al. (2025). Quantitative monitoring of photo-oxidative degradation of Cadmium yellow oil paintings using spectroscopic techniques and mathematical modelling, TECHNART 2025, Perugia (Italia) (poster presentation).
- 71) Carboni Marri S. (2025). The alteration processes of green copper-arsenite pigments in 19th-20th century oil paintings, 23-24/01/2025, Convegno del Partenariato Esteso CHANGES, Roma (Italia) (poster presentation).
- 72) Mattana S. et al. (2025). Monitoring photochemical aging of CdS-based mock-ups by combining experimental spectroscopic studies and mathematical modelling, 23-24/01/2025, Convegno del Partenariato Esteso CHANGES, Roma (Italia) (poster presentation).
- 73) Monico L. et al., Predict and prevent the color changes in paintings by a combined experimental and computational/mathematical modeling approach, 23-24/01/2025, Convegno del Partenariato Esteso CHANGES, Roma (Italia) (oral presentation).
- 74) Monico L. et al., TEY-XANES spectroscopy as a direct method to probe the composition of altered surface of paintings, 16-17/10/2024, Science@CERIC 2024 Symposium, Lecce (Italia) (oral presentation).
- 75) Monico L. et al. (2024). Synchrotron radiation-based X-ray techniques & cultural heritage objects: an integrated multi-material, multi-technique and multi-scale approach to study their composition and evolution, 16-26/09/2024, XVII School on Synchrotron Radiation “Gilberto Vlaic”: Fundamentals, Methods and Applications, Muggia–Trieste (Italia) (oral presentation).
- 76) Monico L. et al. (2023). Prevent the color changes in paintings: a multi-material, multi-technique and multi-scale approach, XX Congresso Nazionale della Divisione di Chimica dell'Ambiente e dei Beni Culturali, Società Chimica Italiana, Ischia (Italia) (oral presentation).
- 77) Monico L. et al. (2023). A combined experimental and computational modeling approach to study the color change of painted surfaces, 11-15/09/2023, INdAM International Workshop–MACH2023 Mathematical modeling and Analysis of degradation and restoration in Cultural Heritage, Roma (Italia) (oral presentation).

OPD

- 78) Mugnaini S., Brancolini T., Caruso O., Galeotti M., Pieralli I., Porcinai S., Cucci C., Piccolo M., Stefani L. (2025). Sulphidation and protection of silver artefacts: correlations between film properties and protective efficacy under different environmental conditions, Workshop “Sustainable Diagnostics and Cultural Heritage: Achievements and Perspectives of CHANGES Spoke 5”, Catania (Italy), 28-30 October 2025 (oral presentation)

- 79) Mugnaini S., Brancolini T., Caruso O., Galeotti M., Pieralli I., Porcinai S., Cucci C., Picollo M., Stefani L. (2025). Solfurazione e protezione di manufatti in argento: correlazioni tra proprietà di film polimerici ed efficacia protettiva in differenti condizioni ambientali, Workshop “Per un restauro sostenibile: il progetto CHANGES PNRR Next-generation EU”, Florence (Italy), 25-26 November 2025 (oral presentation).

48

UNIBO

- 80) Prati S. (2026). Cutting Edge Diagnostic Approaches and Greener Restoration Materials: towards Sustainable Practices in Cultural Heritage, Mappe e scenari per il futuro del patrimonio Culturale, Roma
- 81) Prati S. (2025). Towards sustainable practice in cultural heritage: innovative diagnostic approaches and eco-friendly restoration materials. Sustainable Diagnostics and Cultural Heritage”, spoke 5; Catania
- 82) Prati S. (2025). La chimica applicata alla conservazione e valorizzazione del patrimonio culturali: nuovi approcci diagnostici e materiali avanzati. Fiera del Restauro, Ferrara.

UNICT

- 83) Belfiore C. M., Callieri M., D’Agostino G., Menta S., Potenziani M., Santagati C., Scopigno R. (2026). A 3D-based Web Platform for Multi-Source and Multi-Sensor Diagnostic Data Fusion and Visualization, 3D-ARCH 2026, 11th International ISPRS/CIPA Workshop “3D virtual reconstruction and Visualization of Complex Architectures”, Ancona 10-12 February 2026 (oral presentation).
- 84) Belfiore C. M., Callieri M., D’Agostino G., Menta S., Potenziani M., Santagati C., Scopigno R. (2026). A 3D-based Web Platform as an innovative tool to support the Management and Visualization of Multi-source Diagnostic Data, Convegno Tematico AIAR OrganicaMente Pisa, 4 – 6 February 2026 (poster presentation).
- 85) Belfiore C. M., Menta S., Stroschio A. (2026). An experimental approach to unravel the decaying behavior of ancient mortars from the historic built heritage of Catania (Sicily), Congresso finale CHANGES, Roma 14-16 January 2026 (oral presentation).
- 86) Belfiore C. M., Callieri M., D’Agostino G., Galizia M., Gueli A., Menta S., Politi G., Potenziani M., Salerno G., Santagati C., Scopigno R., Trigona C. (2025). Web-Based 3D Visualization for Integrated Cultural Heritage Diagnostics, Congresso finale CHANGES, Roma 14-16 January 2026 (oral presentation).
- 87) Fugazzotto M., Occhipinti R., Belfiore C. M., Barone G., Mazzoleni P. (2025). CHANGES: materiali ad attivazione alcalina per il restauro del Monastero dei Benedettini di San Nicolò l’Arena in Catania, Giornate GABeC 2025 “Scienza e conservazione dei geomateriali nei Beni Culturali”, Napoli 4-5 december 2025 (oral presentation).
- 88) Trigona C., Karoui M. A., Politi G., Gueli A. M., Belfiore C. M. (2025). Performance Analysis of Thermoelectric Generators Coupled with Pietra di Modica for Thermal Gradient Enhancement, IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for Sustainability, Benevento 4-5 December 2025 (poster presentation).
- 89) Menta S., Stroschio A., Ortolano G., Visalli R., Belfiore C. M. (2025). Influence of aggregate grain size on the hydraulic behavior of lime mortars. BeGEO Conference “Working for the Future Challenges in Earth Sciences”, 3rd Conference of Young Geoscientists, Napoli 17-18 November 2025 (oral presentation).

- 90) Belfiore C. M., Menta S., Stroschio A. (2025). An experimental approach to unravel the decaying behavior of ancient mortars from the historic built heritage of Catania (Sicily), Workshop "Sustainable Diagnostics and Cultural Heritage Achievements and Perspectives of CHANGES Spoke 5", Catania 28-30 October 2025 (oral presentation).
- 91) Belfiore C. M., Callieri M., D'Agostino G., Menta S., Potenziani M., Santagati C., Scopigno R. (2025). Strumenti digitali per la visualizzazione dei dati diagnostici dei materiali da costruzione: l'esempio delle malte del centro storico di Catania, Workshop "Sustainable Diagnostics and Cultural Heritage Achievements and Perspectives of CHANGES Spoke 5", Catania 28-30 October 2025 (oral presentation).
- 92) Menta S., Stroschio A., Ortolano G., Visalli R., Belfiore C. M. (2025). Assessing material compatibility in restoration: comparing hydraulic properties of repair and historic mortars, 3rd Workshop on Advanced X-ray Characterization Technologies in Earth Sciences, Catania 22-24 October 2025 (poster presentation).
- 93) Menta S., Stroschio A., Ortolano G., Visalli R., Belfiore C. M. (2025). Assessing material compatibility for restoration: An innovative approach to compare hydraulic properties of repair and historic mortars. 2025 IMEKO TC26 International Conference on Metrology for Archaeology and Cultural Heritage, Bergamo, October 15-17, 2025 (oral presentation).
- 94) Menta S., Stroschio A., Belfiore C. M. (2025). From heritage to laboratory: reproduction of ancient lime mortars for durability studies, International Workshop "Mathematical tools for Cultural Heritage", Roma 6-8 October 2025 (invited oral presentation).
- 95) Menta S., Stroschio A., Ortolano G., Visalli R., Belfiore C. M. (2025). An innovative approach to compare hydraulic properties of repair mortars and historic mortars: A case study from the historical city center of Catania. Congresso congiunto SIMP-SGI 'Le Geoscienze e le sfide del XXI secolo', Padova 16-18 September 2025 (poster presentation).
- 96) Menta S., Stroschio A., Mazzoleni P., Ortolano G., Visalli R., Belfiore C. M. (2025). Hydraulic properties of experimental lime mortars with differently sized volcanic aggregates: Insights from a multi-analytical approach. 7th Historic Mortars Conference (HMC 2025), Padova, 2-4 September 2025 (oral presentation).
- 97) Belfiore C. M., Menta S., Stroschio A. (2025). Diagnostic study of lime mortar samples from historical buildings in Catania (Sicily) through an experimental approach, Convegno "Patrimonio culturale al futuro: sostenibilità sociale, innovazione tecnologica, trasformazione digitale. Le ricerche in corso nel Progetto CHANGES", Roma 23 - 24 January 2025 (poster presentation).
- 98) Menta S., Stroschio A., Mazzoleni P., Belfiore C. M. (2024). "Reproduction of ancient lime mortars from the Baroque built heritage of Catania (Sicily): an experimental study", Congresso congiunto SGI-SIMP, Geology for a sustainable management of our Planet, Bari 3-5 September 2024 (oral presentation).
- 99) Occhipinti R., Belfiore C. M., Fugazzotto M., Barone G., Mazzoleni P. (2024). "The mortars as a marker of the evolution over time of materials and construction techniques in the Benedictine Monastery of Catania", Congresso congiunto SGI-SIMP, Geology for a sustainable management of our Planet, Bari 3-5 September 2024 (oral presentation).

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- 100) Bretti G., Belfiore C. M. (2025). Mathematical modelling of the water absorption properties for historical lime-based mortars from Catania (Sicily, Italy), Convegno "Patrimonio culturale al futuro: sostenibilità sociale, innovazione tecnologica, trasformazione digitale. Le ricerche in corso nel Progetto CHANGES", Roma 23 - 24 gennaio 2025 (poster presentation).

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- 101) Pizzimenti, S., Cipolletta, B., Fiore, M., Alberico, M., Morelli, M., Giardina, P., Cicatiello, P., Thomas, B., Carpentieri, A., Tokarski, C., Di Pasquale, G., Birolo, L., Vergara, A. (2025). The challenge of organic residue analysis in archaeology and a novel approach for minimally invasive protein sampling for mass spectrometry imaging. Workshop "Sustainable Diagnostics and Cultural Heritage: Achievements and Perspectives of CHANGES Spoke 5", Catania, Italy, 28–30 October 2025. (Oral presentation)
- 102) Sannino, M. F., Alberico, M., Diglio, F., Fragiasso, F., Vergara, A., Bellia, L., Palella, B. I., Riccio, G., Pollio, A. (2025). Characterizing potential biodeteriogenic fungi from heritage contexts: VExperimental evaluations for sustainable conservation. Workshop "Sustainable Diagnostics and Cultural Heritage: Achievements and Perspectives of CHANGES Spoke 5", Catania, Italy, 28–30 October 2025.
- 103) Alberico, M., Cipolletta, B., Rossi, M., Viola, P., Tortino, G., Birolo, L., Pizzimenti, S., Carpentieri, A., Manzone, A., Vergara, A. (2025). Chemical diagnostics at the Royal Palace of Caserta. XXI Congresso Nazionale della Divisione di Chimica dell'Ambiente e dei Beni Culturali, Cremona, Italy, 10–13 September 2025. (Oral presentation)
- 104) Alberico, M., Bellia, L., Diglio, F., Fragiasso, F., Pizzimenti, S., Harputluoğlu, E. R., Vergara, A. (2025). Developing a framework to study color variations in ancient ink: Preliminary analysis. XX Conferenza del Colore, Naples, Italy, 4–5 September 2025. (Oral presentation)
- 105) Vergara, A., Capozzi, F., Alberico, M., Gaglione, A., Granata, A., Manzone, A., Viola, P., Giordano, S., Spagnuolo, V. (2025). Biomonitoring microplastics and black crust occurrence on outdoor sculptures. 19th International Conference on Chemistry and the Environment, Belgrade, Serbia, 8–12 June 2025. (Oral presentation)
- 106) Sannino, M. F., Bellia, L. (2025). Tecniche radiometriche per la diagnosi e la ricerca di strategie volte alla limitazione di effetti fotobiologici. CATACOMBE e IPOGEI – Facciamo luce sul controllo dei potenziali biodeteriogeni in epoca di cambiamenti climatici, IGIC, Catacombe di Domitilla, Rome, Italy, 28 May 2025. (Oral presentation)
- 107) Alberico, M., Cipolletta, B., Sannino, M. F., Rossi, M., Tortino, G., Pironti, C., Carpentieri, A., Pollio, A., Birolo, L., Vergara, A. (2025). Mixed iron-based inks: Insights into the role of carbon and its effects on ink degradation mechanisms. TECHNART 2025 – International Conference on Analytical Techniques for Heritage Studies and Conservation, Perugia, Italy, 6–9 May 2025. (Poster)
- 108) Cipolletta, B., Thomas, B., Ntasi, G., Cicatiello, P., Giardina, P., Tokarski, C., Birolo, L. (2025). Immobilized trypsin-enhanced MALDI-imaging analysis of surfaces and cross-sections of works of art. TECHNART 2025 – International Conference on Analytical Techniques for Heritage Studies and Conservation, Perugia, Italy, 6–9 May 2025. (Poster)
- 109) Alberico, M., Cipolletta, B., Rossi, M., Tortino, G., Pironti, C., Carpentieri, A., Pollio, A., Birolo, L., Vergara, A. (2025). Diagnostics and degradation mechanism of XVIII century inks. Convegno "Patrimonio culturale al futuro – Progetto CHANGES", Rome, Italy, 23–24 January 2025. (Poster)
- 110) Birolo, L. (2025). Collagen deamidation: Animal glue versus tanned leather versus "cooked" bones. Janeiro na Madeira Meeting 2025, Madeira, Portugal, 26–29 January 2025. (Oral presentation)
- 111) Cipolletta, B., Alberico, M., Vergara, A., Birolo, L. (2025). Paleoproteomics and cultural heritage: Open questions and challenges. Convegno "Patrimonio culturale al futuro – Progetto CHANGES", Rome, Italy, 23–24 January 2025. (Oral presentation)

- 112) Sannino, M. F., Colesanti, G. T., Capone, G., De Natale, A., Di Concilio, F., Pollio, A. (2025). Assessing microbiological degradation of paper: A study of fungal contamination in Campania libraries. Congress “Patrimonio culturale al futuro: sostenibilità sociale, innovazione tecnologica, trasformazione digitale – Progetto CHANGES”, Rome, Italy, 23–24 January 2025.
- 113) Alberico, M., Cipolletta, B., Rossi, M., Tortino, G., Carpentieri, A., Pollio, A., Birolo, L., Vergara, A. (2024). On the degradation mechanism of XVIII century inks. EUCHEMS Congress, Dublin, Ireland, July 2024.
- 114) Birolo, L., Cipolletta, B., Ntasi, G. (2024). Ancient proteins: Current challenges in identification and characterization. 48th FEBS Congress, Milan, Italy, 29 June – 3 July 2024.
- 115) Sannino, M. F., Petrarretti, M. G., De Natale, A., Pollio, A. (2024). La diversità dei funghi coltivabili che popolano archivi e biblioteche italiane nell’ambito del progetto PNRR-CHANGES – Spoke 5. XXIV Convegno Nazionale di Micologia, Legnaro (Padua), Italy, 20–21 June 2024.
- 116) Alberico, M., Cipolletta, B., Rossi, M., Tortino, G., Carpentieri, A., Pollio, A., Birolo, L., Vergara, A. (2024). Degradation process of documents written in the XVIII century. INART Conference, Oslo, Norway, 4–7 June 2024.
- 117) Alberico, M., Cipolletta, B., Rossi, M., Tortino, G., Carpentieri, A., Birolo, L., Vergara, A. (2024). The Vanvitelli’s ink recipe. INART Conference, Oslo, Norway, 4–7 June 2024. (Oral presentation)
- 118) Cappelletti, P., Izzo, F., Rispoli, C., Pollio, A., De Natale, A., Petrarretti, M., Carpentieri, A., Birolo, L., Melchiorre, C., Ferraro, G., Manzone, A., Vergara, A. (2023). A pre-restoration minero-petrographic, chemical and microbiological analysis of the sculpture “Real Infante Carlo Tito di Borbone”. IMEKO International Conference on MetroArchaeo 2023, Rome, Italy, 19–21 October 2023.
- 119) Cipolletta, B., Fiore, M., Ntasi, G., Botto, M., Birolo, L., Tirabassi, L. (2023). The challenge of extracting proteins from potteries. IMEKO International Conference on MetroArchaeo 2023, Rome, Italy, 19–21 October 2023.
- 120) Cipolletta, B., Fiore, M., Ntasi, G., Botto, M., Birolo, L., Tirabassi, L. (2023). Current analytical challenges for the identification of organic residues in archaeological pottery. XX Congresso Nazionale della Divisione di Chimica dell’Ambiente e dei Beni Culturali, Ischia, Italy, 28 September – 1 October 2023.
- 121) Birolo, L., Ntasi, G., Cipolletta, B., Aprea, C., Dello Iorio, L., Marino, G., Vergara, A., Bonaduce, I. (2023). Molecular characterization of collagen-based animal glues by proteomics and spectroscopic analyses. XX Congresso Nazionale della Divisione di Chimica dell’Ambiente e dei Beni Culturali, Ischia, Italy, 28 September – 1 October 2023.

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- 122) Medeghini L., Di Fazio M., Tomasini R., Masi A. (2025). Unveiling the Past: An Interdisciplinary Archaeometric Approach at the Cencelle Archaeological Site, 4th International conference TMMCH 2025 - Transdisciplinary Multispectral Modelling and Cooperation for the Preservation of Cultural Heritage (oral presentation).
- 123) Di Fazio M., Calzolari L., Capriotti S., Rea C., Medeghini L. (2025). Integrated IR Multi-Methods Protocol for Cultural Heritage Geomaterials: Evaluation of Statistical Data Processing, 4th International conference TMMCH 2025 - Transdisciplinary Multispectral Modelling and Cooperation for the Preservation of Cultural Heritage (oral presentation).

- 124) Di Fazio M., Calzolari L., Capriotti S., Rea C., Bastida Armesto M., Medeghini L. (2025). Comprehensive IR multi-method approach for mortars of cultural heritage interest, Congresso congiunto SIMP-SGI 2025 - Geosciences and the Challenges of the 21st Century, Abstract book (poster presentation).
- 125) Fiorani D., Lemorini C., Masi A., Medeghini L., Sadori L., Cerafogli E., Di Fazio M., Porrovecchio C., Previti G., Vaccariello A. (2025). From Field to Lab: Cross-Disciplinary Protocols, Issues and Solutions for the Architectural and Archaeological Study of Cultural Heritage, Sustainable Diagnostics and Cultural Heritage Achievements and Perspectives of CHANGES Spoke 5, Catania, 28-30 Ottobre 2025 (oral presentation).
- 126) Di Fazio M., Calzolari L., Rea C., Capriotti S. & Medeghini L. (2024). Evaluation of an IR multi-methods protocol for the study of Cultural Heritage, Congresso congiunto SGI-SIMP, Abstract book (2024) (poster presentation).
- 127) Rea C., Di Fazio M., Mercuri L., Calzolari L., Capriotti S., Mignardi S., Dallai L., Stasolla F.R., Medeghini L. (2024). Archaeometric investigation of lithic materials from the archaeological site of the Holy Sepulchre (Jerusalem), Congresso congiunto SGI-SIMP, Abstract book (2024) (oral presentation).
- 128) Rea C., Bastida Armesto M., Calzolari L., Di Fazio M., Capriotti S., Mignardi S., Stasolla F.R., Medeghini L. (2024). Statistical analysis of IR spectra of mortar for studying the relationship between building phases, Congresso congiunto SGI-SIMP, Abstract book (2024) (poster presentation).
- 129) Rea C., Calzolari L., Capriotti S., De Vito C., Aurisicchio C., Mignardi S., Medeghini L. (2024). Application of infrared external reflection spectroscopy in the identification of emerald provenance, Congresso congiunto SGI-SIMP, Abstract book (2024) (poster presentation).
- 130) Masi A., Cerafogli E., Di Fazio M., Sadori L., Stasolla F. R., Medeghini L. (2024). Unveiling the Holy Sepulchre's Past: A Multidisciplinary Approach to Characterise Mortars and Wood Remains, MetroArchaeo 2024 – International Conference on Metrology for Archaeology and Cultural Heritage (oral presentation).
- 131) Medeghini L., Di Fazio M., Calzolari L., Rea C., Capriotti S., Mignardi S. (2024). Statistical processing of IR data for the definition of an integrated protocol in the analysis of geomaterials, MetroArchaeo 2024 – International Conference on Metrology for Archaeology and Cultural Heritage (oral presentation).
- 132) Fiorani D., Lemorini C., Masi A., Medeghini L., Cerafogli E., Di Fazio M., Porrovecchio C., Previti G., Vaccariello A. (2024). Towards the creation of a relational database for cross-disciplinary interpretation of data and the definition of multi-method protocols, Convegno del Partenariato Esteso CHANGES (oral presentation).